

Letters of Collaboration Index

Attached are 15 letters of collaboration indicating extraordinary support of this proposed work. These letters span major Earth and environmental science cyber infrastructures for the three selected disciplines in the US, UK, Europe, and Australia. Additional letters include NSF FAIROS RCN project specifically focused on PIDs for instruments, Scientific Societies, and other Organizations.

These letters represent the foundational organizations both nationally and internationally working on disciplinary-specific data sharing. Letters representing cyberinfrastructure (repositories) all have established networking standards and protocols for data, and are now moving to enhance the machine-to-machine interoperability and reusability of data to enable scalability of their data in regards to volumes of data being analyzed and diversity of data types.

The final section in the list are the organizations the Principal Investigators and members of the Network Collaborator Committee are involved with and will leverage as part of this work.

Hydrology

- **Consortium of Universities for the Advancement of Hydrologic Sciences Incorporated (CUAHSI):** CUAHSI facilitates the interdisciplinary advancement of water science by making it easier for the water science community to do their work. We do this by providing education and outreach programs, like workshops and grants, as well as specialized software and services to share and access data, collaborate online, and compute in the cloud. CUAHSI's community consists of students, educators, volunteer scientists, outreach coordinators, environmental and watershed organizations, and corporate entities. All who are involved in water science, water-resources management, or water-resources protection and enhancement are part of the CUAHSI community.

CUAHSI provides data and software solutions to support many different science workflows and use cases. Capabilities have been developed to support all aspects of the data management life cycle, from collecting, storing, and analyzing data, to sharing, publishing, and citing data, thereby enabling reproducibility in the water sciences.

- **Environmental Data Initiative:** The Environmental Data Initiative (EDI) is a collaboration between the University of New Mexico and the University of Wisconsin – Madison, Center for Limnology. Their commitment to open environmental data has enabled EDI to become a leading resource for researchers and educators worldwide. By fostering collaboration and providing essential infrastructure, these institutions empower the advancement of ecological understanding and promote informed decision-making for a sustainable future.

EDI provides key services and technical expertise to the scientific community that ensure environmental and ecological data are well curated and accessible for discovery and re-use well into the future. We assist researchers from field stations, individual laboratories, and research projects of all sizes to archive and publish their environmental data. EDI is committed to make data FAIR.

We provide support, training, and resources to help archive and publish high-quality data and metadata. We operate a secure data repository and work closely with other leaders in information management, like the LTER Network Office and DataONE, to promote data management best

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practices and stewardship. Our team consists of highly motivated and experienced data practitioners, software developers, and research scientists.

Oceans

- **British Oceanographic Data Centre:** The British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) is a national facility for looking after and distributing data concerning the marine environment. BODC is certified as a Trustworthy Data Repository by the CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. We preserve and distribute a wealth of publicly accessible data.
- **British Antarctic Survey:** British Antarctic Survey (BAS), an institute of the Natural Environment Research Council (UKRI-NERC)*, delivers and enables world-leading interdisciplinary research in the Polar Regions. Its skilled science and support staff based in Cambridge, Antarctica and the Arctic, work together to deliver research that uses the Polar Regions to advance our understanding of Earth and our impact on it.

Seismology

- **National French Seismological Data Center, ISTERre:** The Institute of Earth Sciences (ISTERre) is a joint research unit of the CNRS, Grenoble-Alpes University, the University of Savoie Mont Blanc, the IRD, and Gustave Eiffel University. ISTERre is a leading laboratory for Grenoble's Universe Sciences Observatory (OSUG) whose research focuses primarily on the physical and chemical study of the planet Earth.
- **AuScope:** AuScope is Australia's provider of research infrastructure to the national geoscience community working on fundamental geoscience questions and grand challenges — climate change, natural resources security and natural hazards.
- **EarthScope:** EarthScope Consortium is a global community of employees, scientists, scholars, and educators. Our goal is to advance understanding of the Earth and its physical systems by democratizing access to geophysical instrumentation, observations, and practices.
- **Swiss Seismological Service:** The Swiss Seismological Service (SED) at ETH Zurich is the federal agency responsible for monitoring earthquakes in Switzerland and its neighboring regions and for assessing Switzerland's seismic hazard and risk.

Cross-Discipline

- **PANGAEA:** The information system PANGAEA is operated as an Open Access library aimed at archiving, publishing and distributing georeferenced data from earth system research. PANGAEA guarantees long-term availability (greater than 10 years) of its content. PANGAEA is open to any project, institution, or individual scientist to use or to archive and publish data. PANGAEA focuses on georeferenced observational and experimental data. Citability, comprehensive metadata descriptions, interoperability of data and metadata, a high degree of structural and semantic harmonization of the data inventory as well as the commitment of the hosting institutions ensures FAIRness of archived data.

NSF FAIROS RCNs

- **FAIR Facilities and Instruments, FAIROS RCN:** This research coordination network (RCN) will advance the standardization and adoption of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for research facilities and instruments nationally. PIDs are widely seen as foundational to open science in that PIDs uniquely identify various entities in the research ecosystem.

Scientific Societies and Organizations

- **Committee on Data for Science and Technology (CODATA):** CODATA is the Committee on Data of the **International Science Council (ISC)**. CODATA exists to promote global

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collaboration to improve the availability and usability of data for all areas of research. CODATA supports the principle that data produced by research and susceptible to be used for research should be as open as possible and as closed as necessary. CODATA works also to advance the interoperability and the usability of such data: research data should be **intelligently open** or **FAIR**. By promoting the policy, technological and cultural changes that are essential to promote Open Science, CODATA helps advance ISC's vision and mission of advancing science as a global public good.

The **CODATA Strategic Plan** identifies three priority areas:

1. promoting principles, policies and practices for Open Data and Open Science;
 2. advancing the frontiers of data science;
 3. building capacity for Open Science by improving data skills and the functions of national science systems needed to support open data.
- **Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP):** ESIP is a home for Earth science data professionals. As a nonprofit funded by cooperative agreements with NASA, NOAA, and USGS, we bring together interdisciplinary collaborations to share technical knowledge and engage with data users.
 - **European Geosciences Union, Earth and Space Science Informatics Division (EGU ESSI):** As far as informatics and information technology are concerned, the ESSI Division deals with community-driven and multidisciplinary challenges and solutions. This includes topics like: data model and metadata standardisation, spatial data infrastructure interoperability, semantics services, quality and uncertainty information encoding and propagation, geospatial data processing, environmental model accessibility, big data management, and data visualisation for scientific discovery.
 - **World Data System (WDS):** The mission of WDS is to promote long-term stewardship of, and universal and equitable access to, quality-assured scientific data and data services, products, and information across all disciplines in the Natural and Social Sciences, and the Humanities.

Data Reuse Researcher

- **Dr. Ixchel M. Faniel:** Ixchel M. Faniel's research interests include improving how people discover, access and use/reuse content. She is currently examining how academics manage, share and reuse research data and librarians' experiences designing and delivering supportive research data management programs.

Organizations represented by the PIs and Network Collaborator Committee Member

- **Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research:** The Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI) conducts polar and marine research from the atmosphere to the deep sea. Climate research for us and future generations.
- **Australian National University**
- **Coalition for Publishing Data in the Earth and Space Sciences (COPDESS):** The Coalition for Publishing Data in the Earth and Space Sciences (COPDESS) is a collaboration among research repositories, scholarly publishers, and other stakeholders focused on jointly developing, implementing, and promoting leading practices around the preservation and citation of data, software, and physical samples that lead toward credit and reuse in the Earth, space, and environmental sciences. Focus areas include: 1) Citation practices for research outputs including data, software, and samples in scientific publications, 2) Best practices and resources for journal editors and staff, 3) Support domain repositories in the Earth, environmental, and space sciences, 4) Connect researchers with appropriate repositories; and 5) Improving the workflows around

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FAIR scientific data and software and especially for between data repository discovery, ingest and curation, and journal peer review, publication, and post-publication linking and discovery.

- **American Geophysical Union Informatics Section (AGU Informatics Section):** The Informatics Section is concerned with evolving issues of data management and analysis, technologies and methodologies, large-scale computational experimentation and modeling, and hardware and software infrastructure needs, which ultimately provide the capability to change data systems into knowledge systems that support the range of Earth and space science interests. The Informatics Section fosters the solutions to these issues to enable transparent and reproducible earth and space science.
- **Biological Chemical Oceanographic – Data Management Office (BCO-DMO), Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute (WHOI):** The Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office (BCO-DMO) is a trustworthy, publicly-accessible, domain science data repository created to curate, publish, and archive digital data and information from biological, chemical, and biogeochemical research conducted in coastal, marine, Great Lakes, and laboratory environments. The office provides services that span the full data life cycle, from data management planning support and DOI creation, to archive with appropriate long-term facilities. Repository staff work closely with investigators to help them prepare, publish, and share their data and related information for reuse.
- **International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange (IODE):** The International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange (IODE) of the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO was established in 1961. Its purpose is to enhance marine research, exploitation and development, by facilitating the exchange of oceanographic data and information between participating Member States, and by meeting the needs of users for data and information products.
- **Internet of Water:** The Internet of Water Coalition is a group of organizations working together with federal, state, and local government partners to build foundational water data infrastructure across the US and create a community of people and organizations using water data to make better decisions.
- **National Academy Board on Research Data and Information (BRDI):** The mission of National Academy Policy and Global Affairs Board on Research Data and Information (BRDI) is to improve the stewardship, policy, and use of digital data and information for science and the broader society. The Board does this through the following tasks:
 - Address emerging issues in the management, policy, and use of research data and information at the national and international levels;
 - Through studies and reports of the National Academies, provide independent and objective advice, reviews of programs, and assessment of priorities concerning research data and information activities and interests of its sponsors;
 - Encourage and facilitate collaboration across disciplines, sectors, and nations with regard to common interests in research data and information activities;
 - Monitor, assess, and contribute to the development of U.S. government and research community positions on research data and information programs and policies;
 - Initiate or respond to requests for consensus studies, workshops, conferences, and other activities within the Board’s mission, and provide oversight for the activities performed under the Board’s auspices; and

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- Broadly disseminate and communicate the results of the Board's activities to its stakeholders and to the general public.
- **National Academies Roundtable on Aligning Incentives for Open Scholarship:** The Roundtable on Aligning Incentives for Open Scholarship convenes critical stakeholders to discuss the effectiveness of current incentives for adopting open science practices, current barriers of all types, and ways to move forward to optimally align reward structures and institutional values.
- **National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) of the Australian National University**
- **National Oceanography Centre, UK**
- **Ocean Network Canada:** Ocean Networks Canada (ONC) is a world-leading ocean observing facility hosted and owned by the University of Victoria (UVic), and managed and operated by the ONC Society, a not-for-profit established in 2007. ONC delivers ocean data from its cabled, mobile and community-based observing networks that represent an essential component of Canada's ocean observing science capacity.
- **RDA Organizational Assembly:** Organizational Members provide an organizational perspective of the RDA, influence its direction, and assist in the implementation and adoption of the RDA's Recommendations. For many global organizations the RDA is a vehicle to help incorporate solutions and practices for data sharing and reuse.
- **RDA Fair Data Maturity Model Working Group:** The FDMM WG has published the core criteria to assess the implementation level of the FAIR data principles. The working group is now supporting this product and adopters.
- **RDA/ESIP Earth, Space, and Environmental Interest Group (ESES IG):** The ESES IG is currently in transition to the Earth, Space and Environmental Sciences Data (ESES) Community of Practice (CoP). The ESSE CoP is focused on improving data and software management and sharing practices that result in our researchers having access to community informatics resources that support their research. This CoP will provide a place for individuals, teams and organizations in the Earth, space, and environmental research ecosystem to coordinate on common challenges, share information, review and consider RDA Recommendations, seek leading practices, and work towards finding approaches to discipline-specific challenges and issues around data and software management and sharing. The international Earth, space, and environmental community is broad and includes researchers, data managers, data curators, institutions, instrument creators and manufacturers, software developers, tools, repositories, journal editors and more.
- **RDA Complex Citation Working Group:** This RDA working group has recently published their recommendation on what is needed to address the problem when an author wants to include 40+ digital object citations in a manuscript, and the journal practices force long lists of citations into the supplementary information.
- **RDA Coordinating Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Data Preservation and Scholarly Publication Processes Working Group (Repo2Pub):** This working group aims to improve collaboration and coordination between repository and publisher workflows as they pertain to- and rely upon the data publication process. The group proposes to refine and formally document a detailed workflow(s) between the journal, publication author, and Earth, Space, and Environmental Science disciplinary data repository and identify cross-stakeholder dependencies to recommend activities that are necessary for relevant processes to move forward in a more coordinated way.

Jordan S Read, PhD (he/his)
Executive Director, CUAHSI
(339) 933-4660
jread@cuahsi.org
<https://www.cuahsi.org/>

Friday, February 6th, 2025

To: The National Science Foundation

If the proposal submitted by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia, entitled ***“GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities”*** is selected for funding by NSF, it is my intent to collaborate as detailed in the proposal’s Project Description, or the Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources section of the proposal.

Signed: _____ Print Name: Jordan S Read

Date: 02/06/25 Organization: CUAHSI

Environmental Data Initiative

Create · Package · Archive · Discover · Reuse

7 February 2025

Subject: Letter of Collaboration

Dear Panel Reviewer,

If the proposal submitted by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia, entitled ***“GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities”*** is selected for funding by NSF, it is my intent to collaborate as detailed in the proposal’s Project Description, or the Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources section of the proposal.

Sincerely,

Paul C. Hanson
pchanson@wisc.edu
EDI Lead Principal Investigator
Distinguished Professor of Research
University of Wisconsin - Madison, Center for Limnology
680 N Park St., Madison, WI 53706

National Oceanography Centre
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7 February 2025

Subject: Letter of Collaboration

Dear Panel Reviewer,

If the proposal submitted by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia, entitled “***GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities***” is selected for funding by NSF, it is my intent to collaborate as detailed in the proposal’s Project Description, or the Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources section of the proposal.

Sincerely,

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink on a light grey background, appearing to read "Justin J. H. Buck".

Dr Justin J. H. Buck
Principal Robotics Engineer
justin.buck@noc.ac.uk

**British
Antarctic Survey**

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

High Cross, Madingley Road
Cambridge, CB3 0ET
United Kingdom

www.bas.ac.uk

7th February 2025

Subject: Letter of Collaboration

Dear Panel Reviewer,

If the proposal submitted by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia, entitled “GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities” is selected for funding by NSF, it is my intent to collaborate as detailed in the proposal’s Project Description, or the Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources section of the proposal.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "A. Frémand".

Alice Frémand
almand@bas.ac.uk

Scientific Data Manager (Geophysics)
Chair of the AGU Data Management Advisory Board

UK Polar Data Centre,
British Antarctic Survey
High Cross, Madingley Road
Cambridge, CB3 0ET
United Kingdom

Institut des Sciences de la Terre

National Science Foundation, USA

7 February 2025

Subject: Letter of Collaboration

Dear Panel Reviewer,

If the proposal submitted by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia, entitled "GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities" is selected for funding by NSF, it is my intent to collaborate as detailed in the proposal's Project Description, or the Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources section of the proposal.

Sincerely,

Signature

Helle Pedersen
helle.pedersen@univ-grenoble-alpes.fr
Professor
Director of the national French seismological data center

ISTerre

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Unité Mixte de Recherche
CNRS / UGA / IRD / USMB / UGE
UMR5275 / UR219

7 February 2025

Subject: Letter of Collaboration

Dear Panel Reviewer,

If the proposal submitted by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia, entitled **“GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities”** is selected for funding by NSF, it is my intent to collaborate as detailed in the proposal’s Project Description, or the Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources section of the proposal.

Yours sincerely,

Dr Tim Rawling
CEO AuScope Limited
tim@auscope.org.au
c/o Melbourne Connect
Level 3, 700 Swanston St Carlton
Victoria 3053 Australia

26 June 2024

To the National Science Foundation,

If the proposal submitted by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia entitled “EAGER: Forging Data Repository and Journal Publication Community Partnerships to Leverage Research Cyberinfrastructure: Improving Researcher Data Publication and Citation Practices” is selected for funding by NSF, it is EarthScope Consortium’s intent to collaborate and/or commit resources as detailed in the Project Description or the Facilities, Equipment or Other Resources section of the proposal. This collaboration and/or commitment is limited to the time that EarthScope Consortium has cooperative agreements with the NSF to operate geophysical facilities. The SAGE and GAGE facilities, which are operated by the EarthScope Consortium, will terminate at the close of September 2025. The NSF has announced its intention to support a National Geophysical Facility (NGF) that will continue providing NSF-funded investigators with geophysical instrumentation, project planning, and other engineering support after the close of the SAGE and GAGE facilities. Commitments for support extended by the SAGE and GAGE facilities may carry forward to the future NGF but are contingent on the specific implementation of that facility by NSF.

Sincerely,

David Mencin
Vice President of Data Services
EarthScope Consortium

Schweizerischer Erdbebendienst
Service Sismologique Suisse
Servizio Sismico Svizzero
Swiss Seismological Service

ETH

Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich
Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich

U.S. National Science Foundation
Directorate for Geosciences
NSF 25-506: Geosciences Open Science
Ecosystem (GEO OSE)
Panel Reviewer

Schweizerischer Erdbebendienst
ETH Zürich
Florian Haslinger

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8092 Zürich
Switzerland

Telefon: +41 44 633 4670
E-Mail: florian.haslinger@sed.ethz.ch
www.seismo.ethz.ch

Zürich, 10 February 2025

Subject: Letter of Collaboration

Dear Panel Reviewer,

If the proposal submitted by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia, entitled "***GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities***" is selected for funding by NSF, it is my intent to collaborate as detailed in the proposal's Project Description, or the Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources section of the proposal.

Sincerely,

Florian Haslinger

florian.haslinger@sed.ethz.ch
Deputy Director
Schweizerischer Erdbebendienst
ETH Zürich
Switzerland

Alfred Wegener Institute, PO Box 12 01 61, 27515 Bremerhaven, Germany

Shelly Stall
AGU

07. February 2025

Subject: Letter of Collaboration

Dr. Frank Oliver Glöckner
Prof. for Earth System Data
Science
Head of Data at the Computing
and Data Center
Head of PANGAEA

Phone: +49/471-4831-1459
Email:
frank.oliver.gloeckner@awi.de

Dear Panel Reviewer,

If the proposal submitted by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia, entitled "GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities" is selected for funding by NSF, it is my intent to collaborate as detailed in the proposal's Project Description, or the Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources section of the proposal.

With best regards

Prof. Dr. Frank Oliver Glöckner

Alfred Wegener Institute
Helmholtz Centre for
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<http://www.library.ucar.edu>

7 February 2025

Subject: Letter of Collaboration

Dear Panel Reviewer,

If the proposal submitted by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia, entitled ***“GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities”*** is selected for funding by NSF, it is my intent to collaborate as detailed in the proposal’s Project Description, or the Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources section of the proposal.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Matthew S. Mayernik".

Dr. Matthew S. Mayernik
Deputy Library Director and Research Data Services Specialist
NSF National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR)
University Corporation for Atmospheric Research (UCAR)
P.O. Box 3000
Boulder, CO 80307-3000
E-mail: mayernik@ucar.edu

7 February 2025

Subject: Letter of Collaboration

Dear Panel Reviewer,

If the proposal submitted by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia, entitled “GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities” is selected for funding by NSF, it is my intent to collaborate as detailed in the proposal’s Project Description, or the Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources section of the proposal.

Sincerely,

Dr. Simon Hodson

simon@codata.org

Executive Director

CODATA, the Committee on Data of the International Science Council

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Subject: Letter of Collaboration

Dear Panel Reviewer,

If the proposal submitted by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia, entitled “GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities” is selected for funding by NSF, it is my intent to collaborate as detailed in the proposal’s Project Description, or the Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources section of the proposal.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Susan Shingledecker', written in a cursive style.

Susan Shingledecker
susanshingledecker@esipfed.org
Executive Director
Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP)
574F Ritchie Hwy #248
Severna Park, MD 21146

National Science Foundation
2415 Eisenhower Avenue
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USA

Your contact

Dr Jens Klump

Division President, Earth and Space Science
Informatics

essi@egu.eu
www.egu.eu

07 February 2025

Subject: Letter of Collaboration

Dear Panel Reviewer,

If the proposal submitted by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia, entitled "***GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities***" is selected for funding by NSF, it is my intent to collaborate as detailed in the proposal's Project Description, or the Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources section of the proposal.

Sincerely,

Dr. Jens Klump
essi@egu.eu
Division President, Earth and Space Science Informatics
European Geosciences Union
Kastenbauerstr. 2
81677 Munich
Germany

11 February 2025

Subject: Letter of Collaboration

Dear Panel Reviewer,

If the proposal submitted by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia, entitled **“GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities”** is selected for funding by NSF, the World Data System intends to collaborate as detailed in the proposal’s Project Description, or the Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources section of the proposal.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read "M. P. Goins".

Meredith P. Goins, MSIS
mgoins2@utk.edu
Executive Director, World Data System

11 February 2025

Subject: Letter of Collaboration

Dear Panel Reviewer,

If the proposal submitted by Shelley Stall, Danie Kinkade, and Natalie Raia, entitled “***GEO OSE Track 1: Forging Cross-Stakeholder Partnerships to Accelerate Geoscience Discoveries: Cultivating Sustainable Disciplinary Open Science Communities***” is selected for funding by NSF, it is our intent to have Dr. Ixchel Faniel, Senior Research Scientist, OCLC collaborate on the project. Dr. Faniel will participate in a virtual orientation session, sharing findings and insights from her research on disciplinary data re-use behaviors, as detailed in the proposal’s Project Description.

We are pleased to support this important work to advance and accelerate scientific collaboration.

Sincerely,

Constance Malpas

Constance Malpas
Executive Director, Research & Programming
OCLC
malpasc@oclc.org